

Investigating the role of pulsed electric fields as radiosensitizers of medulloblastoma cancer stem cells

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Cancer stem cells (CSCs) constitute an endless reserve for the maintenance and progression of tumors and, moreover, they could be the reason of conventional therapy failure. Therefore, new therapeutic strategies are necessary to targeting specifically CSCs.

To this aim, pulsed electric fields of different durations (in the microsecond and nanosecond time scale) have been selected to exposure D283Med cells, a human medulloblastoma (MB) cell line resulted to be a reservoir of CSCs, and normal human astrocytes. Thus, we analyzed *in vitro* different endpoints at different times after the exposure as cell viability/proliferation, cell cycle, clonogenicity as well as the expression of different genes involved in cell cycle, apoptosis and differentiation. Results showed that microsecond pulsed electric field (μ PEF) exposure (using the following parameters: 40 μ s, 0.35 MV/m, 5 pulses) was able to induce after 24 hrs, exclusively in MB CSCs, cell death and, in the survival cells, a transitory G2/M cell-cycle arrest with a senescence-associated phenotype via the up-regulation of GADD45a. Furthermore, selective targeting of μ PEF-exposed D283Med cells was also validated *in vivo* in a heterotopic mice xenograft model, resulting in a significant tumor volume reduction with no eradication of tumor mass. Concomitantly to the μ PEF-associated cell damage (24 hrs), we finally tested the efficacy of μ PEF to make cells more susceptible to ionizing radiation exposure, both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Our data open to novel therapeutic options for the targeting of MB CSCs, indicating non-ionizing electric fields pre-exposure as an effective means to overcome radio-resistance of CSCs.

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